

Micro-frontends Workshop

1 Exercise

The exercise consists of adding a new form field to the general tab (*ProjectGeneralComponent*) of the project-info micro-frontend as represented in the picture bellow.

DADOS DE ENTRADA DO PROJETO | Mercury

GERAL DADOS GEOMETRIA

Nome: *
Mercury

Id do projeto de referência: *
admin

Campo do workshop: *
workshop1

Descrição:
Interpretação sísmica objetivando identificação dos horizontes.

It is an editable text box that represents a new field (**workshopField**) of the *Project* object present on the *microfrontends-project-library*. A version of the library (**0.0.4-workshop**), containing the new field, has already been generated.

Additionally, in order to facilitate the exercise, *workshop* branches on both the **shell** and **project-info** applications have been created with updated mocked databases containing the new field and the workshop version of the project library already installed.

2 Environment Setup

Before starting the exercise, it will be necessary to clone and install both the shell application and the project-info micro-frontend. For the entirety of the exercise a connection with our internal network is necessary (VPN or Remote Access).

2.1 Shell Setup

Clone the repository by running the command:

```
git clone https://redacted.address/module-federation/shell.git
```

Then, inside the *shell* folder, switch to the workshop branch and run the install command:

```
git checkout workshop  
npm i
```

Once the application is installed you can test it by running the start command:

```
npm run start
```

The application will open in a new window and fetch the micro-frontend from the machine determined on the environments file. Each one of them can be accessed individually from your browser.

2.2 Project Info Setup

For the development of the feature proposed on the exercise it will be necessary to have a local version of the *project-info* micro-frontend. So there will be a similar process for installing it.

First clone the application:

```
git clone https://redacted.address/module-federation/project-info.git
```

Then, inside the *project-info* folder, switch to the workshop branch and run the install command:

```
git checkout workshop  
npm i
```

Once the application is installed you can test it by running the serve command:

```
npm run serve
```

The application will be available on your browser on the URL `http://localhost:4202/`, followed by the id of the project you would like to access.

Ex: `http://localhost:4202/proj1`

2.3 Configuring the Shell to Use Local Microfrontend

Once you wish to start testing your changes done to your local micro-frontend on the shell application, you will require to update its path on the shell's **environment.ts** file. Update the line:

```
projectInfoUrl: 'http://redacted_machine:30002'
```

To point to your micro-frontend's URL:

```
http://localhost:4202
```

Once reloaded, the shell application will fetch the micro-frontend from the newly specified URL.

3 Class Information

The the general tab (**ProjectGeneralComponent**) requires an input form to work. This form is instantiated by the micro-frontend's main component (**ProjectInfoComponent**), using the **FormService**. The form generated for the general component will require a new form field in order to handle the **workshopField**.

Additionally, in order to update the project's data, the general component uses the **ProjectFeatureService**'s update method. So, in order for the update to go through after the user clicks on the confirm button, it will be necessary to adjust some methods of the **ProjectGeneralComponent**.